

bands appearing at 1 660(w) and 1 560(m) cm^{-1} in the free ligand are one due to amide-I and the other amide-II bands¹⁸. In the complexes, these two bands are in the strong and broad bands covering the region 1 680–1 550 cm^{-1} . The peak appearing at 3 130–2 900 cm^{-1} in the free ligand is due to the NH_3^+ stretching frequency which comes from the zwitterion $^-\text{OOC}-\text{C}-\text{NH}_3^+$ of the amino acid moiety¹⁹. This zwitterion form was also supported by the appearance of NH_3^+ symmetric and asymmetric deformation vibration at 1 530 and 1 620 cm^{-1} , respectively. There was no band due to free NH_3 group in the ligands. But in the complexes the bands corresponding to NH_3 disappeared and bands around 3 300, 1 600(bs) and 1 300 cm^{-1} corresponding to the stretching, bending and wagging mode of vibrations of the coordinated NH_3 group²⁰ were observed. Thus the zwitterion moiety in the free ligand changed to NH_3 in the complexes. The strong band at 1 720(s) cm^{-1} in the free ligand was due to asymmetric vibration of COOH (non-amino acid)²⁰ and the band at 1 600(s) cm^{-1} is due to asymmetric stretching of COO^- group in amino acid part²². In the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes, there was no band at 1 720 cm^{-1} , instead strong and broad bands around 1 600 cm^{-1} were observed. This indicates that coordination occurred between the two acid groups through the deprotonation of COOH group of the non-amino acids part, the $-\text{COO}^-$ group of the amino acid part remaining unbonded. The ν_{SH} band at 2 500 cm^{-1} in glutathione disappeared on complexation. This indicated the linking of metal to sulphur (thiol) in all these complexes. The $\text{C}-\text{S}$ stretching frequency appeared in the 690–610 cm^{-1} region^{23,24} in the spectrum of glutathione. In the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, there was an additional band due to the coordinated water²¹ observed at 960 cm^{-1} which was absent in the ir spectra of complexes of other metals and also in the free ligand.

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Stepwise Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of the Chelates of L-Lysine Monohydrochloride with Iron(II), Strontium(II) and Antimony(III)

K. D. JAIN and USHA SHARMA*

Department of Chemistry, D. A. V. College, Dehradun-248 001

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COMPLEXATION behaviour of L-lysine has been extensively studied¹⁻⁵. A perusal of literature has revealed that no work has been reported on the metal chelates of L-lysine monohydrochloride. However, Jain *et al.*^{6,7} have reported the studies of some new metal chelates with L-lysine monohydrochloride.

The present work describes the thermodynamic functions of Fe^{II} , Sr^{II} and Sb^{III} with L-lysine monohydrochloride.

Experimental

All chemicals were of B.D.H. quality. Solutions of L-lysine monohydrochloride and metal nitrate/chloride were prepared in double-distilled water. The pH-metric investigations were carried out in aqueous media in the temperature range $15-30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using carbonate-free 1 M NaOH. A constant ionic strength of 1 M was maintained by adding an appropriate quantity of potassium nitrate/chloride solu-

TABLE I—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS AND STABILITY CONSTANT OF METAL—L-LYSINE MONOHYDROCHLORIDE SYSTEMS

Metal ion	Stability constants of proton/metal complexes	Temp. (°C)		-ΔG° kcal mol ⁻¹		ΔH° kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS° cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		15°	30°	15°	30°	at 30°	at 30°
Fe ^{II}	log K ₁	5.76	5.14	7.54	6.68	-22.84	-57.42
	log K ₂	2.87	2.65				
Sr ^{II}	log K ₁	5.25	5.16	6.89	7.27	+2.49	+32.90
	log K ₂	2.99	2.73				
Sb ^{III}	log K ₁	3.08	2.95	10.98	11.82	+2.13	+45.87
	log K ₂	2.86	3.20				

tion. Stability constants of metal and proton complexes were determined by using Bjerrum Calvin technique⁹. pH of the solution was measured with Metram Harisan E-520 pH meter.

Results and Discussion

The ligand dissociates as

The carboxylic group of the acid does not form the conjugate base intramolecularly, indicating practically the absence of any dipolar form. Presence of a single inflection on titrating the acid with strong base in aqueous media contributes to the foregoing view.

Examination of the pH-metric curves displayed a separation of metal—ligand curve from acid curve. This contributes to the fact that the protons liberation is due to the complexation value of $\bar{n}$ increased gradually in all cases. This amounts to the involvement of anionic form of the acid in complexation, the $\bar{n}$ value of 2 for Fe^{II} and Sr^{II} L-lysine monohydrochloride system and of 3 for Sb^{III} L-lysine monohydrochloride system indicating the presence of complexes of 1:2 and 1:3 stoichiometry, respectively. Analysis of formation curves ($\bar{n}$ vs pL) indicates that there was not much difference in the values of successive stability constants. The calculations of stepwise formation therefore could not be done by Bjerrum integral method ($\log K_1/K_2$, 2.5)⁹. Further, it was seen that the formation curves less their wave character justify the similarity in the successive formation constants. Even the system of higher complexity Sb^{III} L-lysine monohydrochloride ($\bar{n}=3$) could not fulfil the conditions, i.e. $K_1 - K_2$. (i) $\log K = -\log(L^-)$ at $\bar{n}=0.5$, (ii) $-\Delta G^\circ = RT \log K$.

The value of $-\Delta G^\circ$ for Fe^{II} decreases with the increase of temperature. Whereas the value of $-\Delta G^\circ$ for Sr^{II} and Sb^{III} L-lysine monohydrochloride system increase with the rise of temperature. The enthalpy (ΔH°) is positive for Sr^{II} and Sb^{III} L-lysine monohydrochloride system justifying the endothermic nature of these reactions. The positive

value of ΔS° for Sr^{II} and Sb^{III} only favours the formation of the complexes¹⁰. Table I contains the mean value of stability constants of metal and proton complexes at different temperatures and their thermodynamic functions.

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Additive and Antagonistic Effects of Mixtures of Cationic and Anionic Surfactants in the Suppression of Positive Polarographic Maximum of Thallium(I) *vis-a-vis* the Adsorption Characteristics

(MISS) INDU BALA and MUKHTAR SINGH*

Chemistry Department, Agra College, Agra-282 002

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THOUGH several workers¹⁻³ have attempted the suppression of positive polarographic maximum of Tl^I by a number of ionic and non-ionic surfactants, no attempt has been made so far to study the suppressive behaviour of mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants in respect of positive maxima. In this paper, we report the results of our